
Indian Governance

Ajit Arjun Pawar¹ & Mahesh M. Lohar²

¹S. G. M. College, Karad, Tal - Karad Dist - Satara

²Kakasaheb Chavan College, Talmavale Tal - Patan Dist - Satara

Corresponding Author – Ajit Arjun Pawar

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15544319

Abstract:

A critical discussion about the form of Indian governance is often held among students and experts of political science whether governance in India is "federal" or "unitary". Along with this, it is also true that along with parliamentary governance, federal governance has been a topic of discussion from the very beginning. In this research paper, we will study how federal governance has been made to give constitutional powers to social and cultural diversity locally, while transitional unitary governance has been provided to deal with emergencies. Ultimately, parliamentary governance has been adopted to enable the diversity of the country to participate in governance at the national level. In this way, it has been studied in the research paper that the Indian governance system is not a pure form of governance, but a synthesis of parliamentary governance, unitary governance, and federal governance.

Keyword: Indian Governance, Socio-Physical Environment, Unitary Governance etc.

Introduction:

This topic is discussed among scholars of political science about the form of the Indian political system whether there is federal governance or unitary governance here. Along with this, it is also important that following Britain, a parliamentary system of governance has also been adopted here. In the research paper, it has been studied that the aim of the constitution makers here was not to maintain the purity of any form of governance but to keep in mind the need for diversity in the country's social, cultural diversity, and geographical structure and the unity and integrity of the country, important aspects of three forms of governance, unitary governance, federal governance, and parliamentary governance have been included as per the need.

Objectives:

1. To study Indian Governance.

2. To study synthesis of different Forms of Governance.
3. To study Socio-physical environment.

Research Methodology:

A descriptive, analytical research method has been used for writing the presented research paper and the information required for it has been obtained through secondary fact collection from various reference books, newspapers, and magazines.

Subject Analysis:

Socio-physical Environment:

First of all, we will study the conditions that existed at the time of independence. In this sequence, as we know socio-cultural multiplicity is found in India. Along with this, diversity is also found in the geographical structure. Because of this, a major problem in front of the constitution makers was how to recognize the diversity

of this newly independent country, so that the goal of independence and united India obtained after a long struggle could also be achieved, because along with the pleasant feeling of independence, India was also suffering the pain of the painful feeling of partition.

In such a situation, there was a need to adopt a system of governance in which local creative aspirations could be respected. There could be the right to govern at their level, so that policymaking could be done according to local needs and their implementation could also be possible with their participation. Apart from this, there was also a need to have such a provision in the constitution, so that the country could be rescued from transitional situations and its unity and integrity could be protected. Keeping both these needs in mind, federal governance was adopted in India, and at the same time unitary aspects have also been included. Along with this, there was also a need to make the diversity of religion, caste, language, region, and gender present in the country a stakeholder in the central government, because by making such an arrangement, active participation of these diversities could be ensured in policy making and its implementation for the entire country.

To fulfill this need, the constitution makers decided to adopt parliamentary governance, because, in this way, all castes, religions, languages, genders, and regions of the country can get participation in the central government. The reason for this is that in this government, it is necessary for the appointment of members of the Council of Ministers to be members of the Parliament. It also happens that only the party having a majority in the lower house has the right to form the government and to get the majority, the party must get the support of almost all castes, religions, genders, and regions. Therefore, the majority party ensures the participation of all the

above in the formation of the government (Council of Ministers including the Prime Minister). Now in the next phase of the research paper, we will study the main characteristics of the above three forms of governance, so that we can make it clear which feature of which form of governance is fulfilling which need of the country. The main characteristics of the three forms of governance in the Indian Constitution - Parliamentary, Federal, and Unitary are as follows.

Unitary Governance:

Along with this, some unitary features are found in the Indian political system. Here, first of all, we will know the meaning of unitary governance. This is the system of governance in which governance is conducted from a single center. Although units exist in this too, they are only agents of the center. There is only one constitution for the entire country. In this, provisions related to the governance of the Union and the State have been made. Whereas in federal governance, the Union as well as the States have their separate constitution. Single citizenship is found. Its advantage is that a citizen living in any corner of the country is a citizen of the country only and not of the state. A unified judicial system is also found. The advantage of this is that every citizen of the country is loyal to the judiciary. At this stage of the research paper, we will try to connect the above three forms of governance in addition to India's social structure and cultural plurality and see how federal governance has been adopted to give importance at the local level to the diversity in socio-cultural and physical structure, while the basic elements of unitary governance have been adopted to rescue the country from crises and to secure the unity and integrity of the country. Because emergencies require quick decisions, which is best possible only in unitary governance.

The experience of centuries of slavery and the sad experience of partition of

the country immediately after independence has inspired the constitution makers to make such a provision. On the one hand, the constitution makers have provided the constitutional right to the diversity existing in the country to work freely within the constitutional limits by providing federal governance. On the other hand, to prevent disintegration from this diversity, the major aspects of unitary governance have been included to overcome crises. In this sequence, a very important fact is that parliamentary governance was also adopted. There are two important reasons behind its adoption. Firstly, we were gaining experience of this type of governance during the British rule, but the other aspect that is more important than this is how to weave the diversity of the country into one thread. The answer to this question was possible only in parliamentary governance, because in the way of governance organization at the central level, such opportunities exist, which provide opportunities for participation in governance to the diversities of all regions of the country, caste, language, religion, gender, etc. If we look at it in more detail, the clarity will be more. In parliamentary governance, the party that gets a majority in the lower house gets the opportunity to form the government. The majority can be achieved only when the candidates win based on the support of the party from most of the castes, religions, languages, and regions of the country.

In parliamentary governance, the real executive is the Council of Ministers including the Prime Minister. In India, the President appoints the leader of the majority party as the Prime Minister. After this, the Prime Minister takes care of the expansion of his Council of Ministers so that all castes, religions, languages, regions, and genders of the country get opportunities in governance. This is done so that the interests of those communities get representation in governance and their interests get

respectable opportunities in the form of policies. In parliamentary governance, the Council of Ministers which is the executive body has a plurality of members, which is why everyone gets opportunities, whereas in presidential governance, the head of the executive body is the President who is a single person. Therefore, various aspects of the society do not get the opportunity to participate in governance. Keeping these things in mind, the Constitution makers also adopted the parliamentary system of governance.

Conclusion:

On the basis of the above study, we reach the conclusion that while federal governance has been adopted by giving importance to socio-cultural diversity, parliamentary and unitary governance have also been adopted to bind this diversity together at the national level and to deal with crisis situations. Thus, Indian governance is not a pure form of governance but a synthesis of the above three.

References:

1. Srinivasan, K. & Selvan, M.S. (2015). Governance and Development in India: A Review of Studies and Suggestions for Further Research. MIDS.
2. Yadav, S. (2010). Public policy and governance in India: the politics of implementation, *The Indian Journal of Political Science*, 71(2).
3. Kashyap, Subhash C. (2008) "Our Political System" National Book Trust,.
4. Kashyap, Subhash C., (1996) "Towards Good Governance: Need for political reforms", *IJPA Special Issue on Good Governance*.
5. Prasad, R.N., (2002) *Governance of India: Issues and perspectives*, New Delhi: Concept,.
6. Tiwari, A.C., "Good Governance and Audit", in B.P. Mathura (Ed.)
7. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/42753707>